

Water–nutrient nexus between domestic wastewater treatment plants and agriculture: identification of sustainable site locations

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Abstract

In Chile, escalating water scarcity necessitates the exploration of alternative water sources for agriculture, a sector that is highly vulnerable to water stress. Treated wastewater (TWW) is a viable alternative that offers the dual benefit of alleviating the pressure on freshwater resources and supporting agricultural productivity. This study assessed the feasibility of TWW reclamation for agricultural use in south-central Chile. A Geographic Information Systems (GIS) framework was applied to evaluate the spatial suitability across the Maule, Ñuble, and Biobío regions based on technical, environmental, social, and economic constraints. The results identified 1.07 million hectares (15.81 % of the study area) as suitable. Land use (46.03%) and slope (49.66%) were the primary limiting factors, whereas road accessibility (100%) and proximity to residential areas (98.95%) had minimal limitations. This study emphasizes the potential of treated wastewater to establish a water-nutrient nexus, enhance soil fertility, and reduce dependence on freshwater. It also addresses the associated health risks and regulatory challenges. These findings demonstrate the efficacy of geospatial tools for advancing sustainable agricultural practices in water-scarce regions.

Keywords

Agricultural irrigation; Geographic Information Systems (GIS); Nutrients; Reclaimed wastewater

INTRODUCTION

Global agriculture consumes 70% of freshwater, with escalating demand amidst climate change and population growth (FAO, 2011; OECD, 2012). Concurrently, intensive farming depletes soil nutrients and threatens crop yields (Kopittke et al., 2017). Treated wastewater (TWW) offers a strategic solution that provides a reliable water source while supplying essential nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, thereby establishing a valuable water-nutrient nexus. However, a spatial mismatch often exists between wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in urban areas and agricultural zones, which complicates large-scale reclamation and nutrient resource depletion. While the benefits of TWW for irrigation have been documented, planning studies that integrate geospatial, environmental, and socio-economic factors remain limited. Chile has exemplified these challenges. Despite nearly 100% wastewater treatment coverage, less than 1% is reclaimed for agriculture, constrained by logistical and regulatory hurdles (SISS, 2025; Vera-Puerto et al., 2022). This study addresses this gap by developing a GIS-based model to identify the strategic locations for TWW reclamation in Chile. The objectives were to: (1) integrate agricultural and WWTP data to pinpoint high-potential regions, and (2) delineate feasible irrigation zones using technical, social, environmental, and economic criteria to promote sustainable agricultural water and nutrient management. This provides an actionable roadmap for sustainable agriculture and closing of the water-nutrient loop.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The geographical areas selected for the present study correspond to the Maule ($35^{\circ} 25' 36''$ S, $71^{\circ} 40' 18''$ W), Ñuble ($36^{\circ} 37' 00''$ S, $71^{\circ} 57' 00''$ W), and Biobío ($36^{\circ} 46' 22''$ S, $73^{\circ} 03' 47''$ W) regions in south-central Chile, covering approximately 30,000 km², 13,100 km², and 24,000 km², respectively. These regions include native forest protection areas, hydrological networks characterized by the presence of lakes and rivers, and a central transportation artery (Route 5). Administratively, the regions are divided into four, three, and three provinces, with a total of 30 communes in Maule, 21 in Ñuble, and 54 in Biobío. Figure 1 illustrates the geographical zones of the study area.

Figure 1. Location maps of the Maule, Ñuble, and Biobío regions indicate urban areas and wastewater treatment plants.

Suitability criteria and constraints

Site selection for treated wastewater (TWW) irrigation was based on a multi-criteria evaluation within a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) framework. Four key criteria were considered: technical, social, environmental, and economic criteria. Nine constraints were applied for the initial delineation of suitable areas. Technical constraints include soil texture (excluding very high sand or clay content) (Pescod, 1992), soil depth (<25 cm) (Wagesho, 2004), soil salinity (>8 mmhos/cm) (Wagesho, 2004), and slope (>15%), to balance various irrigation methods and erosion risks (Anane et al., 2008; US-EPA, 2006). Social constraints involved a 200 m buffer from residential areas to mitigate public perception issues (Anane et al., 2008; Pedrero et al., 2011), and a 15 km limit from roads. Environmental safeguards include the exclusion of incompatible land use/cover (e.g., urban, forest, and water bodies), a 50 m buffer from surface water (US-EPA, 2006), and areas classified as having “very high” intrinsic aquifer vulnerability according to the DRASTIC index (Aller et al., 1987).

GIS-based suitability analysis

All datasets were harmonized into a consistent coordinate system (UTM–WGS84 Zone 19S) and

raster format. Each constraint layer was converted into a binary grid, where cells violating the constraint were assigned a value of 0 (excluded) and compliant cells were assigned a value of 1. The final constraint map was generated through a weighted overlay by multiplying all binary layers. Only cells retaining a value of 1 across all constraints were considered suitable and retained for subsequent analysis. This Boolean approach efficiently eliminated areas deemed unfeasible for TWW applications, based on predefined technical, environmental, and social safeguards.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The spatial analysis identified a total of 1.07 million hectares (1,065,247.56 ha) as suitable for irrigation with treated wastewater, representing 15.81% of the total study area. The results highlight significant variability in the restrictive impact of the individual constraints.

Land use and land cover (LULC) and slope were the most dominant limiting factors, excluding 46.03% and 49.66% of the area, respectively. In contrast, other constraints, such as proximity to residential areas, excluded less than 31.41% of the territory. Road accessibility was the least restrictive factor, with 100% of the area remaining accessible under the defined threshold.

The spatial distribution of these suitable areas, illustrated in Figures 2 and 3, reveals a heterogeneous pattern. These zones are variably situated in relation to existing agricultural land, wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), and urban centers, and encompass a diverse range of slopes and soil textures suitable for different agricultural practices.

Figure 2. Suitable area for irrigation by treated wastewater according to (a) soil texture, (b) soil depth, (c) soil salinity, (d) slope, (e) proximity to residential areas, (f) road accessibility, (g) land use and land cover, and (h) intrinsic aquifer vulnerability. Black represents the suitable area while white represents the unsuitable area.

Figure 3. Suitable area for irrigation by treated wastewater considering the combined effect of all constraints.

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